

PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT INAN ORGANIZATION

BY

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Abstract

This Study Is On Impact Of Management System On Effective Personnel Management In An Organization. The Total Population For The Study Is 200 Staff Of Ministry Of Communication And Information, Kwara State. The Researcher Used Questionnaires As The Instrument For The Data Collection. Descriptive Survey Research Design Was Adopted For This Study. A Total Of 133 Respondents Made Translators, Technology Coordinators, Human Capacity Building Officers And Senior Staffs Were Used For The Study. The Data Collected Were Presented In Tables and Analyzed Using Simple Percentages and Frequencies.

Keywords: Effective Personnel Management, Organization, Ministry of Communication and Information, Kwara State, Total Population (200 Staff), Questionnaires, Data Collection, Descriptive Survey Research Design.

Introduction

The Management Of Information Technology Plays a Crucial Role, Especially InThe Communication And Information Sectors Such As Government Establishments, Where They Build Their Competitive Advantage On Credibility And Information. Every Aspect Of Management In The Modern Age Relies Heavily On Information To Thrive. Nothing Moves Without Information And It Is Generally Believed That Information Is Power And That He Who Has It Has Power. It Has Even Been Described As a Singular Resource Needed To Develop Other Resources, Including Workers In An Organization. That Is Why **Odger And Keeling (2000)** Deduced That One Way Businesses Meet Information Needs Is To Use Management Information System (Mis). One Approach By Which Organization Can Utilize Company's Capability Is Through The Development Of Management Information System (Mis). There Is No Universally Accepted Definition Of Management Information System (Mis) And Those That Exist Reflect The Emphasis And Perhaps Prejudice Of Their Authors. However, The Term "Management Information System" (Mis) Can Be Seen As a Database Management System Tailored To The Needs Of Managers Or Decision Makers In An Organization. Mis Is a System Using Formalized Procedures To Provide Management At All Levels In All Functions With Appropriate Information Based On Data From

Both Internal And External Sources, To Enable Them To Make Timely And Effective Decisions For Planning, Directing And Controlling The Activities For Which They Are Responsible **Argyris (1991)**. It Should Be Noted From The Above Definition That The Emphasis Is On The Uses To Which The Information Is Put. Planning, Directing And Controlling Are The Essential Ingredients For "Management". In Essence, The Processing Of Data, Information, And Communicating The Resulting Information Directly ToThe User, Is The Key Function Of Mis. It Should, Therefore, Be Noted That Mis Exists In Organizations In Order To Help Them Achieve Objective To Plan And Control Their Processes And Operations, To Help Deal With The Uncertainties, And To Help In Adopting Changing Or Indeed Initiating Change. Essentially, Therefore, Information Has Become a Critical Resource, Just Like Energy, Both Of Which Are Vital To The Wellbeing Of Individuals And Organizations In The Modern World. Like Energy And Politics, Technology Is Changing The Ways In Which Information Is Captured, Processed, Stored, Disseminated And Used Augured By **Charles (2002)**.

Research Design

The Researcher Used Descriptive Research Survey Design In Building Up This Project Work The Choice Of This Research Design Was Considered Appropriate Because Of Its Advantages Of Identifying Attributes

Of a Large Population From a Group Of Individuals. The Design Was Suitable For The Study As The Study Sought To Impact Of Management Information System Effective Personnel Management In An Organization.

Sources Of Data Collection

Data Were Collected From Two Main Sources Namely:

- (i)Primary Source And
- (ii)Secondary Source

Primary Source:

These Are Materials Of Statistical Investigation Which Were Collected By The Research For a Particular Purpose. They Can Be Obtained Through a Survey, Observation Questionnaire Or As Experiment; The Researcher Has Adopted The Questionnaire Method For This Study.

Secondary Source:

These Are Data From Textbook Journal Handset Etc. They Arise As Byproducts Of The Same Other Purposes. Example Administration, Various Other Unpublished Works And Write Ups Were Also Used.

Population Of The Study

Population Of a Study Is a Group Of Persons Or Aggregate Items, Things The Researcher Is Interested In Getting Information On The Study The Impact Of Management Information System Effective Personnel Management In An Organization. 200 Staff Of Ministry Of Communication And Information, Kwara State Was Selected Randomly By The Researcher As The Population Of The Study.

Sample And Sampling Procedure

Sample Is The Set People Or Items Which Constitute Part Of a Given Population Sampling. Due To Large Size Of The Target Population, The Researcher Used The Taro Yamani Formula To Arrive At The Sample Population Of The Study.

$$\begin{aligned}
 n &= \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \\
 n &= \frac{200}{1+200(0.05)^2} \\
 &= \frac{200}{1+200(0.0025)} \\
 &= \frac{200}{1+0.5} = \frac{200}{1.5} = 133.
 \end{aligned}$$

Instrument For Data Collection

The Major Research Instrument Used Is The Questionnaires. This Was Appropriately Moderated. They Staff Were Administered With The Questionnaires To Complete, With Or Without Disclosing Their Identities. The Questionnaire Was Designed To Obtain Sufficient And Relevant Information From The Respondents. The Primary Data Contained Information Extracted From The Questionnaires In Which The Respondents Were Required To Give Specific Answer To a Question By Ticking In Front OfAn Appropriate Answer And Administered The Same On Staff OfThe Organizations. The Questionnaires Contained About 16 Structured Questions Which Were Divided Into Sections A and B

Validation Of The Research Instrument

The Questionnaire Used As The Research Instrument Was Subjected To Face Its Validation. This Research Instrument (Questionnaire) Adopted Was Adequately Checked And Validated By The Supervisor His Contributions And Corrections Were Included Into The Final Draft Of The Research Instrument Used.

Method Of Data Analysis

The Data Collected Was Not An End In Itself But It Served As a Means To An End. The End Being The Use Of The Required Data To Understand The Various Situations It Is With a View To Making Valuable Recommendations And Contributions. To This End, The Data Collected Has To Be Analysis For Any Meaningful Interpretation To Come Out With Some Results. It Is For This Reason That The Following Methods Were Adopted In The Research Project For The Analysis Of The Data Collected. For a Comprehensive Analysis Of Data Collected, Emphasis Was Laid On The Use Of Absolute Numbers Frequencies Of Responses And Percentages. Answers To The Research Questions Were Provided Through The Comparison Of The Percentage Of Workers Response To Each Statement In The Questionnaire Related To Any Specified Question Being Considered. Frequency In This Study Refers To The Arrangement Of Responses In Order Of Magnitude Or Occurrence While Percentage Refers To The Arrangements Of The Responses In Order Of Their Proportion.

The Simple Percentage Method Is Believed To Be Straight Forward Easy To Interpret And Understand Method.

The Researcher Therefore Chooses The Simple Percentage As The Method To Use.

The Formula For Percentage Is Shown As.

$$\% = f/N \times 100/1$$

Where f = Frequency Of Respondents Response

N = Total Number Of Response Of The Sample

100 = Consistency In The Percentage Of Respondents For Each Item Contained In Questions.

Table I

Gender Distribution OfThe Respondents					
Response		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	77	57.9	57.9	57.9
	Female	56	42.1	42.1	100.0
	Total	133	100.0	100.0	

From The Above Table It Shows That 57.9% Of The Respondents Were Male While 42.1% Of The Respondents Were Female.

Question 2

The Positions Held By Respondents

Table Ii

The Positions Held By Respondents					
Response		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Translators	37	27.8	27.8	27.8
	Technology Coordinators	50	37.6	37.6	65.4
	Human Capacity Building Officers	23	17.3	17.3	82.7
	Senior Staffs	23	17.3	17.3	100.0

Total	133	100.0	100.0
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The Above Tables Shown That 37 Respondents Which Represent27.8% Of The Respondents Aretranslators, 50 Respondents Which Represents 37.6 % Are Technology Coordinators23 Respondents Which Represents 17.3% Of The Respondents Are Human Capacity Building Officers, While 23 Respondents Which Represents 17.3% Of The Respondents Senior Staffs

Test Of Hypotheses

There Are No Problems Associated With Management Information System (Mis).

Table Iii

There Are No Problems Associated With Management Information System (Mis).			
Response	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Agreed	40	33.3	6.8
Strongly Agreed	50	33.3	16.8
Disagreed	26	33.3	-7.3
Strongly Disagreed	17	33.3	-16.3
Total	133		

There Are No Problems Associated With Management Information System (Mis).	
Chi-Square	19.331 ^a
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000
a. 0 Cells (0.0%) Have Expected Frequencies Less Than 5. The Minimum Expected Cell Frequency Is 33.3.	

Decision Rule:

There Researcher Therefore Reject The Null Hypothesis That State There Are No Problems Associated With Management Information System

(Mis) As The Calculated Value Of 19.331 Is Greater Than The Critical Value Of 7.82

Therefore The Alternate Hypothesis Is Accepted That State There Are Problems Associated With Management Information System (Mis).

Test Of Hypothesis Two

There Are No Benefits Of Management Information System (Mis) In The Motivation Of Workers

Table V

There Are No Benefits Of Management Information System (Mis) In The Motivation Of Workers			
Response	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Yes	73	44.3	28.7
No	33	44.3	-11.3
Undecided	27	44.3	-17.3
Total	133		

Test Statistics	
	There Are No Benefits Of Management Information System (Mis) In The Motivation Of Workers
Chi-Square	28.211 ^a
Df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000
a. 0 Cells (0.0%) Have Expected Frequencies Less Than 5. The Minimum Expected Cell Frequency Is 44.3.	

Decision Rule:

There Researcher Therefore Reject The Null Hypothesis That State That There Are No Benefits Of Management Information System (Mis) In The Motivation Of Workers as The Calculated Value Of 28.211 Is Greater Than The Critical Value Of 5.99

Therefore The Alternate Hypothesis Is Accepted That State That There Are Benefits Of Management Information System (Mis) In The Motivation Of Workers

Conclusion

Conclusively, Lack Of Management Skills On Mis Process By Most Business Organization In Nigeria Does Not Only Affect The Effective Performance Of Mis But Also Reduce Their Ability To Compete

Favorably In The Market With Their Large Scale Industrialist Counterpart Which Has Been a Major Stumbling Block For The Development And Growth Of Business Organizations In Nigeria.

Recommendation

To Achieve Its Corporate Goals And Objectives, a Company Needs To Serve a Larger Market For Its Products. For The Realization Of This, Business Organization Should Pay More Attention To The Development Of a Good And Formidable Management Information System. Based On The Findings Of This Study, We Recommend That; Because Of The Great Potential Of Mis To Generate Employment For The Masses, Government Should Directly Get Involved In The Financing Of Mis In Most Business Organization To Promote Economic Growth And Development. There Should Be The Introduction And Operation Of Central-Data-Base Management System Through Which Information Can Be Produced And Communicated To Various Users At Any Point In Time Within The Firm. There Should Also Be Flexibility In The Nature/Pattern And Structure Of Management System In Organizations So As To Permit Informed And Easy Information Flow And Accessibility To All Information End-Users, Seminars And Training For The Staff In The Organizations To Improve The Strength In The Organization. Organizations Should Also Pay More Attention To Communication Through The Media Agencies. This Goes a Long Way To Promoting The Company's Control Of The Market. Business Organization In Nigeria Should Develop, Acquire Appropriate And Suitable Computer Software And Program To Meet It Ever Growing Growth And Expansion. In The Same Vein, Skilful And Experienced It Workers Should Be Employed To Manage The It Department Of The Company. This Is Because Without Competent Staffs No Appropriate Impact Can Be Affected In The Company. Finally Enough Time Should Be Allotted For The Transmission Of Information So As To Guide Against Error And There Should Be Effective Communication At All Levels Of The So As To Aid Management Control And Create Good Image. Effective Communication Is Also Essential For Forecasting

Mutual Understanding And Minimizing Conflicts Between Management And Employees.

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